

STUDY OF USE AND DIFFICULTIES FACED BY THE B.ED. STUDENT'S FOR USING THE INTERNET IN TEACHING

Dr.Chandrakant Borase

Associate Professor

College of Education, Nashik

Abstract

The present study was conducted for knowing the use of internet for teaching by the B.Ed. students and what type of difficulties faced by them during using the internet. For this study the sample was 30 male and 30 female B.Ed. students from College of Education, Nashik.

It was found that there is a significant difference between the mean scores of male and female B.Ed. student with respect to their utilization of internet and there is also a significant difference between the mean scores of male and female B.Ed. students with respect to their problems faced during utilization of internet.

Introduction

Information Communication Technology is a compulsory subject in B.Ed. curriculum of Pune University. The students admitted to B.Ed. course are from various disciplines viz. Arts, Science, Commerce, Engineering, Agriculture etc. Also the students from Rural, Hilly and Urban areas. The awareness about Information Communication Technology and Internet is much more crucial among the B.Ed. students as far as the content of ICT is concerned. Use of Internet for teaching-learning process improves the effectiveness, efficiency and quality of teaching. Internet is one of the important tools for teaching; it can facilitate communication and interactions effectively, releasing all types of restrictions. Due to this it is necessary to study the use and difficulties faced by B.Ed. students for using the Internet.

Objectives of the Study

- 1) To find out whether there is any significant difference in the Mean scores of utilization of Internet by the B.Ed. students.
- 2) To find out the problems faced by B.Ed. students during using the Internet.

Hypotheses

- 1) There is no significant difference between the mean scores of male and female B.Ed. students

with respect to their utilization of internet.

- 2) There is no significant difference between the mean scores of the male and female B.Ed. students with respect to their problems faced during utilization of internet.

Sample of the Study

Sample for the study consists of 30 male and 30 female B.Ed.students.i.e. total 60 students from College of Education, Nashik.

Tools used for the Study

Scale developed by researcher for utilization and problems faced for using internet. This scale consists of 18 statements of five point scale. i.e. Strongly Agree, Agree, Undecided, Disagree and Strongly Disagree. In it 10 statements are positive and 08 statements are negative.

This scale includes the statements associated with internet Technology viz. competencies among the students, equipments, utilization, innovative teaching-learning strategies, provision of facilities about the internet etc.

Procedure of the Study

The scale developed by researcher is administered on 60 B.Ed.students. The scale which consists of positive items, the scores were given as 5 for Strongly Agree, 4 for Agree, 3 for Undecided, 2 for Disagree and 1 for Strongly Disagree. For negative items, the scores were given as 5 for Strongly Disagree, 4 for Disagree, 3 for Undecided, 2 for Agree and 1 for Strongly Agree.

Statistical Tools used for Analysis of Data

1. Mean
2. Standard Deviation
3. t-test

Testing of Hypotheses

Hypothesis-1: There is no significant difference between the mean scores of male and female B.Ed. students with respect to their utilization of internet.

Sr. No	Group	No. of Students	Mean	S. D	t-value	Level of Significance
1	Female	30	39	13.7	2.127	0.05
2	Male	30	43	10.3		Significant

The computed t-value at 0.05 level of significance is 2.127, which is more than the table value 2.04 and hence it is significant. Consequently, the hypothesis-1 is rejected and it can be said that there is a significant difference between the mean scores of male and female B.Ed. students with respect to their utilization of internet.

Hypothesis-2:

There is no significant difference between the mean scores of the male and Female B.Ed. students with respect to their problems faced during utilization of internet.

Sr. No	Group	No. of Students	Mean	S.D.	t-value	Level of Significance
1	Female	30	36	21.5	2.273	0.05
2	Male	30	34	12.17		Significant

The computed t-value 2.273 exceeds than the table value 2.04 at 0.05 level of significance and hence it is significant. Therefore the hypothesis-2 is rejected. Therefore it was inferred that there is a significant difference in the mean scores of the male and female B.Ed. students with respect to their problems faced during utilization of internet.

Major Findings of the Study

1. There is a significant difference between the mean scores of male and female B.Ed. students with respect to their utilization of internet.
2. There is a significant difference between the mean scores of male and female B.Ed. students with respect to their problems faced during utilization of internet.

Conclusion

Effective teaching of any subject mainly depends upon the use of new technologies and methods of teaching. Therefore the new methods of teaching like internet technology

should be used by all the teacher. This will result in effective teaching-learning process. Internet facilities should be provided to the B.Ed. students and also the computer literacy programme should be conducted on a large scale in training colleges.

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